

The Long and Short Twentieth Century: An Exploration of Institutional Care¹

“The long 20th century” (F. Braudel) and “the short 20th century” (E. Hobsbawm) – two contrasting metaphors that together reflect the complexity and the multifaceted nature of historical interpretations of this dense period.

To question dominant narratives, shed light on under-researched, forgotten and convoluted histories, and examine the entangled histories (also in plural) behind divides is the aim of the ERC Synergy Project “Leviathan”. The project employs a broad understanding of medicine as a lens through which to investigate the complex processes of medicalization and demedicalization across politics, ideology, economy, and everyday life.

A significant part of this project is the broad topic of institutional care, revealing important insights into societal attitudes, policy decisions, medical practices, and the evolution of care systems over time. By emphasizing the “long 20th century,” we align with the perspective on the continuum of historical long-term developments and the gradual evolution of social, political, and economic structures. Policies regarding institutionalization can be traced back to early charitable practices, particularly during the late medieval period when care for the poor and needy was often managed through religious institutions and local communities. By the 16th and 17th centuries, many European countries began implementing poor laws that formalized local governments’ responsibilities to care for the impoverished and disabled. The Enlightenment period, emphasizing reason, science, and rationality, fostered a belief in the ability to understand human behavior and improve humane care through scientific methods. This intellectual movement marked a significant shift toward institutional care, with an increase in medical specialization, including the es-

¹ The research is within the ERC Project "Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good" (LEVIATHAN). The project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503)

tablishment of pediatrics, the emergence of psy-sciences (psychiatry, psychology), and research on diseases of old age. Parallel developments occurred in sociology, demography, and hygiene.

The industrialization and urbanization of the 19th century led to significant social changes, including increased poverty, crime, and homelessness. In response, governments and reformers began to view institutionalization as a means of addressing public health issues and exerting social control, leading to legislative actions. This shift paved the way for the establishment of specialized institutions, such as almshouses, institutions designed to house the poor, homeless, elderly, and disabled, as well as to provide specialized care for the mentally ill. These institutions aimed to provide care and give support but also to remove these ‘ill’ and problematic individuals and groups from “healthy” society in order to protect it. Biopower – in the understanding introduced by Michel Foucault – as a political technology that enables the control of individuals' bodies and lives, as well as entire populations, expanded. The ‘care-control’ institutions became central to social policy, shaping approaches to (mental) health, poverty, and crime well into the 20th century.

In contrast, the “short century” perspective focuses on the intense period marked by dramatic events, including local conflicts and two World Wars, the Cold War, and the rise and fall of totalitarian and authoritarian regimes. In terms of institutional care, this metaphor implies that significant changes occurred within a relatively brief timeframe, leading to a sense of urgency and immediacy, as well as contradictory and non-linear developments. A closer examination of the “long-short 20th century’ from a transtemporal and transnational perspective is a goal of the “Leviathan” project and this special issue.

Geographically, the issue unites topics and examples from various states east and west of the “Iron Curtain” in Europe – Germany, UK, Austria, Yugoslavia, Albania, Bulgaria, and beyond, including Brazil and the USA.

The case study approach provides bounded explanations of significant cases related to the broad topics of care for different categories of people.

Child care is a major focus in the issue, as children were prioritized, viewed as vital to societal continuity. Contributions on child care begin with Maria Papathanssiou’s thorough insights into “Child- and elderly care in rural Austria during the first decades of the 20th century”. Victoria Shmidt analyses “The vicissitudes of foster care in interwar Yu-

goslavia and the global history of child protection”, focusing on the 1920s-1930s.

David Peace looks in-depth at “Eugenics and Children Reception Centres in Post-War Britain”. Kalinka Anchova analyses an insightful case from Bulgaria in “The Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod for the Rehabilitation of Children with Poliomyelitis”. Hristinka Basheva-Nikolova discusses an experiment from late socialist Bulgaria inspired by foreign practices: “The “Family Children's Home” Experiment – An Alternative to Institutional Care (1984 – 1992).

Felix Berth conducts comparative research on “Residential care for babies and toddlers in the two German states between the 1950s and the 1980s”.

Georgi Todorov provocatively attempts – within the totalitarian scientific paradigm – to summarise the developments of Bulgarian socialist policy towards children with disabilities under the heading of “corruption” by bringing together “Corrupt practices in homes for mentally disabled children and neuropsychiatric hospitals in the 1940 – 1970s People Republic of Bulgaria”.

Sabine Hering introduces a gender perspective by examining the situation of girls in public education in Germany from the late 19 century up to the 1960s, analyzing the many-sided continuities of the general image of girls and women, summarized in the title “Thrift, cleanliness, frugality, sexual abstinence”. Girls in public welfare in Germany [„Sparsamkeit, Sauberkeit, Genügsamkeit, sexuelle Enthaltbarkeit“ Mädchen in der öffentlichen Fürsorge in Deutschland].

Manfred Kappeler provides a long-term perspective in his article with the evocative title “A fatal entanglement – The co-operation between youth welfare and psychiatry in the history of residential care” [Eine verhängnisvolle Verstrickung – Die Zusammenarbeit von Jugendhilfe und Psychiatrie in der Geschichte der Heimerziehung].

Psychiatry played a central role – in both institutionalizing and anti-institutionalizing discourses across all age groups. The case study by Tiago Pires and Maria Eduarda de Freitas Xavier, “Art, culture, and psychopathology: an introduction to the anti-asylum narrative of Brazilian psychiatrist Nise da Silveira” presents a pioneering woman therapist and psychiatrist, who developed an anti-hospitalization therapeutic theory and introduced individual-centered art therapy in practice from the early 1940s onwards.

Gergana Doncheva proposes an intriguing, unconventional way of reading two feature films – the American “One Flew Over the Cuckoo's

Nest" and the Bulgarian "Adaptation" – in “Mental asylum as a social and political metaphor in the cinema from the two sides of the Iron curtain”.

Institutional care can encompass the entire lifespan, from infancy to old age. The issue includes three case studies of institutional care for the elderly – the aforementioned case study on rural Austria by Maria Papanassiou, Inxhi Brisku’s article “From War Wounds to Welfare: Caring for Albania’s Elderly in the Transition to Socialism (1945 – 1950)”, and Denitsa Nencheva’s research on “Aging and institutional care during late socialism: the case of the elderly people’s home in the village of Pelishat, Bulgaria”.

The authors investigate historical phenomena to understand contemporary developments. The article by Elka Goranova and Ivanka Sakareva goes the opposite way – the authors take a closer look at a “new power” method in diagnosing and treating various types of disorders and improving cognitive processes – Neurofeedback – by tracing its deeper roots back to the early 20th century.

All case studies emphasize the importance of primary sources and a narrative-driven account of history. By utilizing a diverse range of historical resources – including normative documents, institutional archival materials, ego-documents as ‘bionarratives,’ correspondence, memoirs, interviews, visual materials, and films – the authors conduct in-depth investigations of specific institutions, events, initiatives, groups, and individuals, providing a thorough understanding of these events in their social, cultural, and political contexts.

Most of the case studies are national but are interpreted in their respective international contexts, highlighting the dynamics of international relations. The study of the particular and specific is combined with the attempt to identify patterns, structures, and regularities. All case studies raise theoretical insights that emphasize the interconnectedness of various factors, highlighting both ruptures as essential continuities across different ideologies, political, and economic regimes.

The ‘red thread’, or the central theme, is the processes of institutionalization and de-institutionalization of care for people in need, for vulnerable individuals and groups. Historically, the balance (or lack thereof) between care and control has changed, along with policies of inclusion and exclusion, evolving definitions of “normal-abnormal” and “able-feeble”, and shifting attitudes toward individual autonomy and rights, as well as changing professional staff-patient relations. Continui-

ties and changes in policies are highlighted through research on actors, specific institutions, and particular events.

Although the main topic of the issue is the closed institution, the contributions don't present traditional institutional history. The establishment of the welfare state and its structures, the process of classifying and separating children or elderly people in residential care institutions, and the formulation of rules and practices were conceived and realised by people: doctors, nurses, social workers, psychiatrists, eugenic activists, politicians, Red Cross officers. The struggle for democratization and the deinstitutionalization process were also carried out by individuals who worked to make people in institutions more visible and to change attitudes towards them. The authors emphasize the importance of the biographies of such figures in the different countries, examining their perspectives, discourses and statements, their power positions and responsibilities for crucial decisions about the lives of people in institutions during the 20th century.

The broad topics included in this special issue were discussed at the international Leviathan project conference "Transformations of Postwar Europe: Medicine, Technologies, and Bodies", held in Sofia on 27 – 30 May 2024, and presented in this issue by Denitsa Nencheva. A vast field of research and comparative analyses has been shaped which is still in its early stages.

As editors we do not wish to diminish the reader's enjoyment of discovering the richness of ideas, hypotheses and source materials by imposing our synthesized view on the individual articles. It is difficult, if not impossible, to propose an overarching editorial narrative that fully encompasses the diverse contributions, as our interpretations may vary greatly depending on our personal experiences, attitudes, and theoretical preferences.

We hope that this issue, with its emphasis on complexities, variations, nuances, interconnections and entanglements, challenges the established "grand narratives" on socialism, capitalism, and the Cold war. Nowadays, "grand narratives" can act as a straightjacket that constrains thought. For new "grand narratives", it is too early.